

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-6-july-2014>

Email us: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

THE GROWTH OF INDIAN LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR AND ITS POTENTIAL THROUGH FDI PARTICIPATION

Shri. S. Sathyeshwar,

Research Scholar, Tumkur University, Tumkur, India

Dr.B.G Satyaprasad,

Director,

G.T Institute of Management Studies and Research, Bangalore, India

INTRODUCTION:

The origin of life insurance in India can be traced back to 1818 with the establishment of the Oriental Life Insurance Company in Calcutta. By 1938, there were 176 insurance companies in India. In 1938, the first comprehensive legislation regarding insurance was introduced with the passing of Insurance Act of 1938 that provided strict State Control over insurance business.

Insurance sector in India grew at a faster pace after independence. In 1956, Government of India brought together 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies under one nationalized monopoly corporation and formed Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) by an Act of Parliament, viz. LIC Act, 1956, with a capital contribution of Rs.5 crore¹.

Insurance is a federal subject in India and Insurance industry in India is governed by Insurance Act, 1938, the Life Insurance Corporation Act, 1956 and General Insurance Business (Nationalization) Act, 1972, Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) Act, 1999.

Objectives of the study:

- To study growth of Indian Insurance sector.
- To study the Market Potential for Insurance Business
- To study the impact of FDI participation in Life Insurance

Research Methodology:

The paper is completely a conceptual one whose basic foundation comes from various secondary sources like research articles in journals, published and unpublished scholarly papers, books, various international and local journals, statistical data provided by IRDA, speeches, newspapers and websites.

First phase of Insurance in India:

The origin of life insurance in India can be traced back to 1818 with the establishment of the Oriental Life Insurance Company in Calcutta. The Bombay Mutual Life Insurance Society that started its business in 1870 was the first company to charge same premium for both Indian and non-Indian lives. In 1912, insurance regulation formally began with the passing of Life Insurance Companies Act and the Provident Fund Act.

By 1938, there were 176 insurance companies in India. In 1938, the first comprehensive legislation regarding insurance was introduced with the passing of Insurance Act of 1938 that provided strict State Control over insurance business. Insurance sector in India grew at a faster pace after independence. In 1956, Government of India brought together 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies under one nationalized monopoly corporation and formed Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) by an Act of Parliament, viz. LIC Act, 1956, with a capital contribution of Rs.5 crore. The (non-life) insurance business/general insurance remained with the private sector till 1972. There were 107 private companies involved in the business of general operations and their operations were restricted to organised trade and industry in large cities.

Milestone of Insurance Regulation after 1911:

1912: First piece of insurance regulation promulgated Indian Life Insurance Company Act, 1912

1928: Promulgation of the Indian Insurance Companies Act.

1938: Insurance Act 1938 introduced the first comprehensive legislation to regulate insurance business in India.

1956: Nationalization of life insurance business in India.

1972: Nationalization of general insurance business in India.

Post New Industrial Policy 1991:

In 1993, the first step towards insurance sector reforms was initiated with the formation of Malhotra Committee, headed by former Finance Secretary and RBI Governor R.N. Malhotra. The committee was formed to evaluate the Indian insurance industry and recommend its future direction with the objective of complementing the reforms initiated in the financial sector. The formation of the Malhotra Committee in 1993 started reforms in the Indian insurance sector. The aim of the Malhotra Committee was to assess the functionality of the Indian insurance sector. This committee was also in charge of recommending the future path of insurance in India. The Malhotra Committee attempted to improve various aspects of the insurance sector, making them more appropriate and effective for the Indian market.

The recommendations of the committee put stress on offering operational autonomy to the insurance service providers and also suggested forming an independent regulatory body The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) to provide greater autonomy to insurance companies in order to improve their performance and enable them to act as independent companies with economic motives.

Milestones of insurance regulations after 1992:

1993: Setting-up of the Malhotra Committee.

1994: Recommendations of Malhotra Committee released.

1995: Setting-up of Mukherjee Committee.

1996: Setting-up of an (interim) Insurance Regulatory Authority (IRA).

1997: Mukherjee Committee Report submitted but not made public.

1997: The Government gives greater autonomy to LIC, GIC and its subsidiaries with regard to the restructuring of boards and flexibility in investment norms aimed at channeling funds to the infrastructure sector.

1998: The cabinet decides to allow 40% foreign equity in private insurance companies 26% to foreign companies and 14% to non-resident Indians (NRIs), overseas corporate bodies (OCBs) and foreign institutional investors (FIIs).

Post 1999 Insurance Sector:

The Insurance Regulatory Development Act, 1999 (IRDA Act) allowed the entry of private companies in the insurance sector, which was so far the sole prerogative of the public sector insurance companies. The act was passed to protect the concerns of holders of insurance policy and also to govern and check the growth of the insurance sector.

This new act allowed the private insurance companies to function in India under the following circumstances:

- The company should be established and registered under the 1956 company Act
- The company should only serve the purpose of life or general insurance or reinsurance business
- The minimum paid up equity capital for serving the purpose of reinsurance business has been decreed at Rs 200 crores
- The average holdings of equity shares by a foreign company or its subsidiaries or nominees should not go above 26% paid up equity capital of the Indian Insurance company.

1999: The Standing Committee headed by Murali Deora decided that foreign equity in private insurance should be limited to 26%. According to the committee recommendations the IRA Act was renamed the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) Act.

1999: During the same year Indian Cabinet cleared IRDA Act.

2000: President gave consent to the IRDA Act.

Present times:

The Indian insurance industry has undergone transformational changes since 2000 when the industry was liberalised. With a one-player market to 24 in 13 years, the industry has witnessed phases of rapid growth along with extent of growth moderation and intensifying competition².

There have also been a number of product and operational innovations necessitated by consumer need and increased competition among the players. Changes in the regulatory environment also had a path-breaking impact on the development of the industry. While the insurance industry still struggles to move

out of the shadows cast by the challenges posed by economic uncertainties of the last few years, the strong fundamentals of the industry augur well for a roadmap to be drawn for sustainable long-term growth.

The decade 2001-10 was characterised by a period of high growth (compound annual growth rate of 31 percent in new business premium) and a flat growth (CAGR of around two percent in new business premium between 2010-12), according to KPMG. There was exponential growth in the first decade of insurance industry liberalization. Backed by innovative products and aggressive expansion of distribution, the life insurance industry grew at jet speed. However, this frenzied growth also brought in its wake issues related to product design, market conduct, complaints of management and the necessity to make course correction for the long term health of the industry.

Regulatory changes were introduced during the past two years and life insurance companies adopted many new customer-centric practices in this period. Product-related changes, first in ULIPs (Unit Linked Insurance Plans) in September 2011 and now in traditional products, will have the biggest impact on the industry.

The new guidelines for both linked and non-linked products are in force from the beginning of year 2014, an extension of three months from earlier specified date. This additional period has ensured that life insurers enter the crucial quarter of Jan-March with a full bouquet of products and the sellers are well trained in the nuances of all these new products.

These product guidelines are in line with the IRDA's regulatory theme of customer orientation and long-term nature of the life insurance business. The guidelines follow two overarching themes of providing Guarantee and enhancing Transparency. The major changes introduced include - Higher Death Benefit, Guaranteed Surrender Value and mandatory Benefit Illustration for all life insurance products³.

The changes related to death benefit and surrender value may marginally reduce the customers' overall maturity benefit, i.e., policy IRR, especially at higher ages but will ensure that life insurance serves the purpose of providing life cover which no other financial instrument offers.

All ULIPs are currently sold mandatorily with a personalised Benefit Illustration. This requirement is now being extended to other product forms. The new guidelines have also provided for setting up a "With Profit Committee" at the board level.

While personalized benefit illustration will provide for greater transparency in the pre-sales discussion, the With Profit Committee is likely to lead to greater governance in the administration of Participating policies. Premium paying term linked distributors' commission will promote the long-term nature of insurance products.

Life Insurance sector Growth in India for the financial year 2012-2013

The future of the Indian insurance sector looks bright. The sector which stood at a strong US\$ 72 billion in 2012 has the potential to grow to US\$ 280 billion by 2020⁴. This growth is driven by India's favourable regulatory environment which guarantees stability and fair play. This environment has given rise to an insurance market which encourages foreign investors to tap into the sector's massive potential.

Ever since the Indian government liberalised the insurance sector in 2000 and opened the doors for private participation, the sector has gone from strength to strength. The resultant competition has provided the consumer with a never-before-seen range of products and providers, and also enhanced service levels markedly.

The health of the insurance sector reflects a country's economy. This sector not only generates long-term funds for infrastructure development, but also increases a country's risk-taking capacity. India's economic growth since the turn of the century is viewed as a significant development in the global economy. This view is helped in no small part by a booming insurance industry.

Growth

Over FY03–FY12, life insurance premiums expanded at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 20.1 per cent.

Source: <http://www.ibef.org/Nov 2013>,

References: Media Reports, Press Releases, IRDA Journal, E&Y report

Market Share

LIC is the market leader, with 70.7 per cent share in FY12.

Source: <http://www.ibef.org/Nov 2013>

References: Media Reports, Press Releases, IRDA Journal, E&Y report

Industry Dynamics

Consistent growth in the insurance sector depends on a few factors. Some of these are:

- Effective distribution channels – The efficiency and cost of the various distribution strategies used by companies are significant to their success in the insurance business. This particularly holds true for the retail business.
- Focus on overall financial inclusion – As time evolves, so must the approach of the insurance sector in India. The objective of the insurance sector should ideally be to offer a broader range of activities to a wider populace.
- Consumer needs and preferences – The growth of India’s insurance industry can be attributed to product innovation, dynamic distribution channels, and vibrant publicity and promotional campaigns run by insurance companies. Benefits attached to the products and the manner in which they are delivered (through various marketing tie-ups) have helped bring customers and insurance companies closer to each other and made the latter more relevant.

The life insurance segment contributes about 4 per cent to India’s gross domestic product (GDP) in terms of total premiums underwritten annually. There are 24 private companies in the segment. The state-

owned Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) dominates the field, with about 71 per cent of the market share, according to Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA).

Key Statistics

- India's life insurance segment collected new business premiums worth Rs 11,742.7 crore (US\$ 1.84 billion) for April–May 2013. Indian insurance companies collected a combined Rs 107,010.7 crore (US\$ 16.85 billion) worth of new premiums for FY 2012–13, according to data released by IRDA.
- Meanwhile, the general insurance industry grew by 19.6 per cent in April–May period of FY 2013–14. Non-life insurers collected premiums worth Rs 13,552.46 crore (US\$ 2.13 billion) in the first two months of the current year, as compared to Rs 11,333.54 crore (US\$ 1.78 billion) during the corresponding period of the previous year.

New Developments/ Product Launches

- Insurance companies will now have more freedom to invest in sectors such as IT and pharmaceuticals. IRDA has increased the sector specific exposure limit for investments to 20 per cent of the insurer's total investment, from the previous 15 per cent.
- The electronic know-your-customer (e-KYC) services used by the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) will be accepted as a valid verification process for insurance, according to IRDA. Through e-KYC, insurance companies can conduct electronic identity verification. The agencies can obtain an electronic identity document of the customer which is digitally signed by the UIDAI. This service enables a quicker and more efficient process for the customer as well as the insurance company.
- The Government of India has passed the Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority (PFRDA) bill that allows foreign investors to hold 26 per cent stake in the insurance sector. The primary objective of the bill is to provide pension cover to a greater percentage of the country's population. The PFRDA bill would also provide subscribers a wider range of investment choices. The bill will provide better regulation of the sector and provide more confidence to investors, according to Mr Yogesh Agarwal, Chairman, PFRDA.
- Aviation insurance is likely to emerge as an important segment in the near future with new players in the market operations and existing players seeking to increase fleet size, according to industry officials. At present, the current market size of aviation insurance hovers around Rs 500 crore (US\$ 78.76 million), a figure that is almost certain to grow as the industry develops further.
- In order to enhance financial inclusion in the country and develop bancassurance as a business, IRDA has facilitated banks to sell insurance policies. Application for the licence required to act as an insurance broker can only be obtained after prior approval from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). Banks would be required to apply under the direct broker category. The licence will be valid for three years.

Life Insurance business for the Period ended December, 2013:

From the table below it can be clearly understood that there is increase in the premium collections across most of the life insurance companies during the period ending Dec 2013.

Business Figures -Life										
Ref: December, 2013						Date: 30-01-2014				
First Year Premium of Life Insurers for the Period ended December, 2013										
First Year Premium of Life Insurers for the Period ended December, 2013										(`crore)
Sl No.	Insurer	Premium			No. of Policies / Schemes			No. of lives covered under Group Schemes		
		For December, 2013	Upto 30th December, 2013	Upto 30th December, 2012	For December, 2013	Upto 30th December, 2013	Upto 30th December, 2012	For December, 2013	Upto 31th December, 2013	Upto 30th December, 2012
1	Bajaj Allianz									

	Individual Single Premium	23.33	159.19	197.63	1465	11688	22850			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	116.19	701.94	719.48	39187	318939	454889			
	Group Single Premium	65.51	485.39	441.41	7	146	235	71340	9132570	6592844
	Group Non-Single Premium	33.26	429.45	449.58	38	361	244	1922833	6297905	3252631
2	ING Vysya									
	Individual Single Premium	15.39	23.32	134.34	34	420	1349			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	54.21	320.02	298.95	17998	130884	126951			
	Group Single Premium	0.05	0.42	0.61	0	0	0	5	43	114
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.24	0.96	0.00	9	22	0	2269	20048	0
3	Reliance Life									
	Individual Single Premium	2.89	51.56	89.62	224	4947	13113			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	120.13	794.50	666.89	67746	451476	530711			
	Group Single Premium	3.48	24.78	26.18	24	149	158	34982	366404	961558
	Group Non-Single Premium	31.91	553.29	129.06	15	123	138	35650	163992	111656
4	SBI Life									
	Individual Single Premium	45.69	271.25	224.38	2890	20165	15372			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	453.14	1854.85	1469.68	133165	662031	558499			
	Group Single Premium	76.19	756.41	1506.24	10	47	63	20645	303101	187522
	Group Non-Single Premium	14.75	151.37	175.64	13	87	92	19981	336805	567468
5	Tata AIA									
	Individual Single Premium	5.03	24.83	22.39	270	1435	1774			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	31.47	183.63	209.32	16031	82836	96597			
	Group Single Premium	1.90	66.24	74.95	2	4	2	1034	86354	116029
	Group Non-Single Premium	15.26	76.67	92.19	15	133	100	51430	135993	198052
6	HDFC Standard									
	Individual Single Premium	24.11	100.09	94.69	24327	169151	112847			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	227.73	1444.50	1920.27	59233	431355	486446			
	Group Single Premium	48.83	980.44	552.63	39	362	317	153549	1569917	960597
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0	0	0	0	0	12
7	ICICI Prudential									
	Individual Single Premium	20.79	130.78	75.75	713	4817	3919			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	383.91	2177.29	2057.47	70237	568510	645521			
	Group Single Premium	13.10	197.76	385.62	13	151	132	108841	527269	1121824
	Group Non-Single Premium	6.80	53.91	617.09	0	4	12	-25	3858	87265
8	Birla Sunlife									

	Individual Single Premium	4.65	22.57	11.64	53	999	704			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	73.51	558.72	653.50	39275	254871	361300			
	Group Single Premium	0.94	10.17	4.30	0	2	1	344	3219	898
	Group Non-Single Premium	20.28	379.62	472.19	24	268	312	77105	568994	586967
9	Aviva									
	Individual Single Premium	0.55	5.09	7.19	96	572	791			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	22.58	161.15	237.59	7905	69837	90976			
	Group Single Premium	0.07	0.77	0.47	0	1	0	79	911	767
	Group Non-Single Premium	11.02	128.04	140.56	8	65	97	92058	977524	390003
10	Kotak Mahindra Old Mutual									
	Individual Single Premium	13.63	110.48	88.85	286	4871	3809			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	50.20	258.49	250.31	15921	86271	92525			
	Group Single Premium	30.61	187.34	123.79	5	32	27	188188	1937870	1828422
	Group Non-Single Premium	19.55	236.36	136.02	59	640	500	440434	1887755	1070313
11	Max LIFE									
	Individual Single Premium	43.86	213.75	163.08	49	216	182			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	203.47	1140.35	996.07	64736	359423	349097			
	Group Single Premium	11.61	101.14	99.15	2	24	16	17393	624563	52507
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.81	24.00	25.66	28	600	755	-5724	1469657	1531141
12	Met Life									
	Individual Single Premium	-0.01	3.22	177.27	5	220	21594			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	50.40	392.20	342.30	16334	134979	123903			
	Group Single Premium	3.71	17.51	2.64	0	0	0	2137	15052	14828
	Group Non-Single Premium	4.89	33.54	29.37	15	162	170	61325	976221	603454
13	Sahara Life									
	Individual Single Premium	3.09	8.36	10.77	613	1817	2395			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	2.96	17.57	23.72	3739	23582	41397			
	Group Single Premium	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.00	0.00	0.01	0	0	3	0	0	275
14	Shriram Life									
	Individual Single Premium	7.95	52.42	92.60	909	6591	11058			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	20.52	126.29	118.43	16106	91455	82442			
	Group Single Premium	4.80	81.55	79.20	3	18	1	19108	291615	337808
	Group Non-Single Premium	1.66	11.71	9.38	8	48	57	130490	743770	521402

15	Bharti Axa Life									
	Individual Single Premium	0.01	0.11	0.21	0	-3	3			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	33.28	192.83	128.14	10299	70314	65776			
	Group Single Premium	9.90	50.02	21.49	0	6	3	3241	19539	8625
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	Future Generali Life									
	Individual Single Premium	6.54	35.55	9.28	617	3673	1282			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	12.34	73.49	73.72	7656	50844	57357			
	Group Single Premium	0.01	0.54	0.13	0	0	0	8	779	27
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.93	32.27	43.62	9	48	35	4793	162403	48031
17	IDBI Federal									
	Individual Single Premium	4.25	39.09	36.97	659	4711	6013			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	33.13	165.60	144.51	13543	74562	67915			
	Group Single Premium	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.22	7.59	18.52	1	21	7	22315	192159	133022
18	Canara HSBC OBC Life									
	Individual Single Premium	0.13	3.77	0.02	4	92	2			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	20.36	183.39	259.18	4178	33640	49325			
	Group Single Premium	1.76	10.97	5.95	0	5	0	1300	6038	1845
	Group Non-Single Premium	14.06	228.39	126.41	4	50	38	9827	180749	122352
19	Aegon Religare									
	Individual Single Premium	0.09	2.29	3.17	9	120	180			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	12.03	76.50	80.36	5025	33621	40348			
	Group Single Premium	0.01	0.11	0.11	0	0	0	8	81	109
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.00	4.31	6.03	0	0	0	0	0	591
20	DLF Pramerica									
	Individual Single Premium	1.13	3.79	1.48	46	270	189			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	10.06	69.34	94.99	6423	45943	69260			
	Group Single Premium	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.12	2.02	0.37	9	84	9	13812	187230	37309
21	Star Union Dai-ichi									
	Individual Single Premium	12.29	55.06	147.93	719	3751	10443			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	49.01	212.65	168.85	17486	94223	96716			
	Group Single Premium	4.46	30.05	35.45	1	5	2	3117	17770	19701

	Group Non-Single Premium	0.54	90.96	28.26	5	27	26	38218	284829	204405
22	IndiaFirst									
	Individual Single Premium	3.70	24.15	34.90	205	1734	2821			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	8.77	70.03	116.88	6228	41991	69235			
	Group Single Premium	47.05	942.48	343.72	28	126	34	669087	1325330	43477
	Group Non-Single Premium	0.00	0.00	28.58	0	0	89	0	0	1034991
23	Edelweiss Tokio									
	Individual Single Premium	0.28	1.51	0.51	22	124	32			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	5.96	35.28	16.21	3000	20079	9689			
	Group Single Premium	0.52	6.19	0.58	0	5	4	94	3278	93
	Group Non-Single Premium	1.05	3.69	2.42	11	116	56	97764	218232	22759
	Private Total									
	Individual Single Premium	239.38	1342.23	1624.66	34215	242381	232722			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	1995.36	11210.60	11046.81	641451	4131666	4566875			
	Group Single Premium	324.53	3950.29	3704.64	134	1083	995	1294500	16231703	12249595
	Group Non-Single Premium	177.35	2448.15	2530.96	271	2859	2740	3014555	14808124	10524099
24	LIC									
	Individual Single Premium	3612.30	11882.81	8893.82	431462	1490507	1204941			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	5289.73	20249.43	19122.77	8111595	28399359	20947976			
	Group Single Premium	7314.71	31204.04	20873.18	0	120	77	48710	795272	576236
	Group Non-Single Premium	1242.14	2438.19	1387.65	2834	20362	17903	3483408	30292994	26445752
	Grand Total									
	Individual Single Premium	3851.68	13225.04	10518.48	465677	1732888	1437663			
	Individual Non-Single Premium	7285.09	31460.03	30169.58	8753046	32531025	25514851			
	Group Single Premium	7639.24	35154.33	24577.81	134	1203	1072	1343210	17026975	12825831
	Group Non-Single Premium	1419.50	4886.35	3918.61	3105	23221	20643	6497963	45101118	36969851

Note: 1. Cumulative premium / No. of policies upto the month is net of cancellations which may occur during the free look period.

2. Compiled on the basis of data submitted by the Insurance companies

Source: IRDA website 30.3.2014

Potential of Indian Insurance Industry:

With a huge population base and large untapped market, insurance industry is a big opportunity area in India for national as well as foreign investors. India is the fifth largest life insurance market in the emerging insurance economies globally and is growing at 35-38% annually. It is estimated that the sector will grow at a compounded average growth rate of 15-20% over the next 15-20 years. This impressive growth in the market has been driven by liberalization, with new player's significantly enhancing product

awareness and promoting consumer education and information. The strong growth potential of the country has also made international players to look at the Indian insurance market. Moreover, saturation of insurance markets in many developed economies has made the Indian market more attractive for international insurance players. An insurance market in many developed countries of the world has made the Indian insurance market more magnetic in terms of international insurance players.

Since the life insurance sector was opened up in 2000, it has now gone through two clear cycles - the first of very high growth (CAGR of over 12 per cent in number of new policies between 2000-10) and then one of substantive moderation (CAGR of over 9 per cent between 2010-12). Despite this, long-term growth prospects for the industry remain intact.

Foreign direct investment

The cap on foreign direct investment (FDI) in the sector is also expected to be increased from 26% to 49%⁵. The Insurance Bill has been approved by the government and is soon likely to be cleared by Parliament. This alone is expected to increase FDI inflow to \$10 billion in the short term.

FDI, combined with accommodating regulations, will encourage more international insurance companies to enter India. Simultaneously, the move will also provide more capital to existing players to expand their reach in tier II and tier III markets. As life insurance is a capital-intensive industry, increased investments will impact efficiency and innovation.

The government has allowed 26 per cent foreign investment in activities related to insurance, like broking, third party administrators and surveyors, and permitted FIIs and NRIs to also invest in insurers within the stipulated cap.

Under the norms notified, 26 per cent foreign investment, including foreign direct investment (FDI), Foreign Institutional Investors (FII) and Non-Resident Indians (NRI) will be allowed under the automatic route in insurance companies, insurance brokers, Third Party Administrators (TPAs), surveyors and loss assessors. Earlier, only FDI under the automatic route was allowed in insurance companies. The companies bringing in foreign investment will have to obtain necessary licence from the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) for undertaking prescribed activities. Insurance brokers are entities which, for remuneration, arrange insurance contracts with insurers or reinsurers on behalf of their clients. TPAs help in facilitating health insurance on behalf of insurers. Surveyors and loss assessors provide technical services to the insurance companies. All these entities are required to obtain a licence from the IRDA for undertaking specific activities. The relaxation falls short of the demand of insurance industry which has been pleading for hiking the FDI cap in the sector to 49 per cent, from 26 per cent at present.

Only 6 per cent⁶ of Indians have insurance cover. Of this, 4.4 per cent have life insurance and 5 per cent have a reasonable health cover. Most small businesses (family-owned) have no insurance. Lakhs of people lose all their savings when disaster strikes. After 66 years of independence, should we not aspire to provide adequate protection to our citizens? Why not good crop insurance for our agriculturists, weather insurance, life cover, health insurance and protection for all our assets? India is woefully underinsured. We need long-term capital to invest in our insurance industry --- which is critical, protects human life and is a key resource for the country's infrastructure.

The insurance Bill is unlikely to be passed in the Parliament session last session before the general elections, few of the insurance executives said ⁷ .

"The expectations of the Bill being passed are low," said Amitabh Chaudhry, managing director and CEO of HDFC Life. A senior life insurance executive said with a possible change in government after the elections, the incoming parties would also look at people-centric reforms first in 2014. "Insurance FDI, if at all comes to the Parliament, will only come by 2015," the official said.

The United Progressive Alliance (UPA) government has said its priority is to pass the anti-corruption Bills that are pending in Parliament. The insurance Bill that seeks to increase the foreign direct investment (FDI) in the sector from 26 per cent to 49 per cent is not on the government's radar at present.

Ananthanarayanan, Managing Director and CEO of Bharti AXA General Insurance, said that earlier they were hopeful of the Bill being passed. But now, if it does not happen, the current state of the economy will continue.

The CEO of a private general insurance company said this decision does not come as a shock since when there were opportunities earlier for it to be passed; the government did not pass it.

This would have been a welcome change for an industry that needs a capital infusion of more than \$12 billion in the next five years, he added. "However, it is clear that this not the government's priority, since they are gearing up for the upcoming elections. Passage of Insurance FDI would not be a game-changer for the vote bank; hence they do not see it as a priority."

When the insurance Bill was first introduced in Parliament in 2008, it faced huge opposition because of the FDI proposal. There were various routes proposed, including models like 23 per cent through foreign institutional investor (FII) route and 26 per cent through FDI. However, Parliament was unable to arrive at a consensus.

The UPA government had also looked at hiking FDI in insurance to 49 per cent, without any increase in voting rights. This, however, was not accepted by the other parties.

Forty-nine per cent FDI for insurance and pension was mooted when Pranab Mukherjee was the finance minister, but the decision to approve the proposal was deferred by the Cabinet.

There are two reasons why India is raising the permissible limits on FDI in various sectors⁸. One is evolutionary: as the economy matures and learns, the earlier caution that either prevented or limited FDI inflows is replaced by confidence.

The second reason is necessity: the government reckons that FDI inflows are more stable than money that ebbs and flows in equity markets. Today, with a current account deficit close to 5% of GDP and export markets looking weak, freer FDI inflows offer one way of attracting long term capital. Raising the ceiling is a good idea.

Insurance is an industry that requires lots of capital to expand, particularly in the life segment. Prudential norms prescribed by the regulator call for capitalisation that goes up as premium collections go up. For the insurance industry to continue to grow in underinsured India, it needs lots more capital.

CONCLUSION:

The insurance business in India is projected to reach Rs 4 trillion (US\$ 63.01 billion) in FY 2013–14, according to Mr T.S.Vijayan, Chairman, IRDA. Total premiums collected by the general and the life insurance industry in FY 2012–2013 amounted to Rs 3.75 trillion (US\$ 59.07 billion). The chairman believes that insurance penetration in India has the potential to rise to 5–6 per cent from the current 3.86 per cent. Life Insurance Council, the industry body of life insurers in the country, has projected a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12–15 per cent over the next five years for the segment. India's insurable population is expected to grow to 750 million by 2020, with life expectancy projected to reach 74 years around the same period. The council believes that this favourable Indian demography would result in more people seeking out life insurance. Also, the council predicts life insurance penetration – percentage of insurance premium to GDP – to reach 5 per cent by 2020 from its current 3.2 per cent.

India is the important emerging insurance markets in the world. Life insurance will grow very rapidly over the next decades in India. The major drivers include sound economic fundamentals, a rising middle-income class, an improving regulatory framework and rising risk awareness. The fundamental regulatory changes in the insurance sector in 1999 were significant for future growth. Despite the restriction of 26% on foreign ownership, large foreign insurers were entered the Indian market. State owned insurance companies still have dominant market positions. But, this would probably change over the next decade.

Confederation of Indian Industry (CII) projects the growth rate for India's insurance industry in FY 2013–14 to be around 5 per cent. It also anticipates 60 per cent of non-life insurance companies to record an average growth of more than 10 per cent. The raising of the foreign direct investment (FDI) limit from 26 per cent to 49 per cent in the sector is viewed as a key element to promote the insurance industry in India.

Besides the impact of regulatory measures, the economy and politics will influence the performance of the life insurance industry. The economy, in the macro sense, may face volatility owing the upcoming general elections in 2014. While the insurance industry is party-agnostic, it does require stable economic conditions to perform, just like most other sector. The next government will need restore investor confidence to take advantage of regulatory reforms.

Further, the 2014-15 Union Budget should exempt life insurance products from taxation to provide investors an incentive to buy a policy. The insurance industry can gain leverage from India's burgeoning population only by providing a special tax window for life insurance policies. While serving the critical mandate of securing against loss of life, the life insurance industry is also a critical contributor in enhancing financial inclusion and funding its infrastructure costs.

The 12th Five Year Plan outlines an expenditure of \$1.2 trillion on infrastructure and is deficient by \$300 billion. The insurance industry will play an important role in earning this budget deficit. Thus, the advancement of the insurance industry will also provide a strong impetus to meet the country's long term infrastructure and financial goals.

The statistics received from the IRDA indicates that there is better growth trend in FDI in life insurance sector and it shows significant growth since 2007-08. Having analyzed in brief the history of insurance sector of the private insurance companies, it becomes pretty evident that the Government is acting as a roadblock to the economic development of the country by not increasing the cap on FDI in the insurance sector to 49%, removing this roadblock will set an impetus to a robust and dynamic insurance market in days to come by.

¹ http://www.irda.gov.in/ADMINCMS/cms/NormalData_Layout.aspx?page=PageNo4&mid=2

² Life insurance in India has major growth potential, Rajesh Sud February 17, 2014, <http://businesstoday.intoday.in/story/max-rajesh-sud-on-life-insurance-in-india/1/203380.html>

³ *Rajesh Sud is chief executive and managing director of Max Life Insurance.*

⁴ <http://www.ibef.org/industry/insurance-sector-india.aspx>

⁵ <http://businesstoday.intoday.in/story/expert-outlook-life-insurance-sector-in-2014-v-manickam/1/201887.html>, V Manickam, Secretary General, Life Insurance Council, Edition: January 2014

⁶ FDI in insurance – pass the Bill now, Sunil Mehta, [Http://Www.Thehindubusinessline.Com/Opinion/Fdi-In-Insurance-Pass-The-Bill-Now/Article5107400.Ece](http://Www.Thehindubusinessline.Com/Opinion/Fdi-In-Insurance-Pass-The-Bill-Now/Article5107400.Ece), former Country Head and Chief Executive of AIG in India, September 8, 2013.

⁷ Insurers see slim chance of getting House nod for FDI in 2014, FDI hike in insurance is not UPA 2's radar M Saraswathy, Mumbai , February 4, 2014 , http://www.business-standard.com/article/finance/insurers-see-slim-chance-of-getting-house-nod-for-fdi-in-2014-114020301046_1.html

⁸ India needs more FDI in insurance sector, ET Bureau Aug 6, 2013, http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2013-08-06/news/41131984_1_fdi-inflows-foreign-direct-investment-insurance-sector

REFERENCES:

- Ahluwalia, M. S. (2002). “Economic Reforms in India since 1991: Has Gradualism Worked?” *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 16, (3), 67-88.
- Bhat, Ramesh.(1996).“Regulation of the private health sector in India.” *International Journal of Health Planning and Management*.11:253-74.
- Bhat, Ramesh (2005) “Insurance Industry in India” Structure performance and future challenges.” *Vikalpa*.30: 3-5.
- Inderjit, singh and Ashwini kumar (2005) “Insurance Sector Reforms Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) (2010). Annual Report, IRDA, Mumbai.
- Sinha, P.K. and Sahoo,S.C.(1994) *Marketing of Life Insurance in India*”. “Service Marketing” Himalaya Publishing House
- Wadhawan, Sahdev. (1987). “Health insurance in India: The case for reform.” *International Labour Review* 126(4):479-94.